

HOLCIM

Low CO₂ materials and Cement Performance

BUILDING PROGRESS FOR PEOPLE AND THE PLANET

| HOLCIM | Low CO₂ Materials | © Holcim 2025 | ASCCENT Summer School, May 2025

Context

What are cement and concrete ? What is its CO2 footprint ?

**CO2 footprint of 1M3 RMX
concrete**

~250 kg_CO2/m3

OVERALL GHG EMISSIONS AND THE CEMENT INDUSTRY

Global greenhouse gas emissions are about **40 Gt per year** (5 t per person)

- Based on the latest IPCC report and GCCA estimates, global CO₂ emissions from **cement production** are estimated to be in the order of **7 - 8 % of total emissions**:
 - 4% → Process emissions: Calcination
 - 3-4% → Combustion of fuels
- This would be in the order of **2 700 million tons in 2019** - roughly the total **emissions of India and Bangladesh** combined
- In comparison, road transport is 15% and fashion 8% of global emissions

Cement & concrete CO2 footprint in EU

gc ca Example Country Low Carbon Ratings for Cement (ExC/GCCA)
Global Warming Potential (kg CO₂ e/t)

gc ca Global Low Carbon Ratings for Concrete (GCCA)

HOLCIM NET ZERO PLEDGE

WITH SCIENCE-BASED TARGETS

HOLCIM CO₂ FOOTPRINT

HOLCIM'S PATHWAY TO NET ZERO

THERE IS NO SILVER BULLET

- efficiency gains in design + construction
- efficiency in concrete
- decarbonization of electricity
- less clinker in cement (clinker factor)
- less CO₂ in clinker (arm, efficiency)
- ccus, other technologies
- passive recarbonation

R&D PROJECTS TO DRIVE DECARBONIZATION AND CIRCULARITY

GREEN OPERATIONS
Decarbonizing Holcim

BUILDING BETTER WITH LESS
Decarbonizing construction

CIRCULAR CONSTRUCTION
Building new from old

MAKING BUILDINGS SUSTAINABLE
Decarbonizing cities

BUILDING A NET ZERO FUTURE WITH SCIENCE-BASED TARGETS

- As the global leader in the industry **key role to play to address today's climate crisis**
- **1st global building materials company to sign the Business Ambition for 1.5°C pledge** with science-based approved intermediate targets aligned with a net zero pathway
- **2030 targets accelerate reduction of CO₂ intensity to exceed 20%¹**
- **Partnership signed with Science Based Target initiative (SBTi)** to develop a roadmap for a 1.5°C future in the cement sector
- **Expansion of actions to full value chain that includes scope 3 emissions**

¹ incl. scope 1 & scope 2 emissions for cement operations vs. 2018

Holcim Innovation Center

HOLCIM INNOVATION CENTER

N°1 PRIVATE R&D FACILITY
IN BUILDING MATERIALS INDUSTRY
NEAR LYON, FRANCE

225

researchers

15,000

m²

22

nationalities

27%

sales <5years

300+

patent families

700

new products/y

21

PhDs in 8
countries in 2024

75%

R&D on CO₂ reduction

120

start-up partners

OUR EXPERTISE

A large scope of lab services and technical skills

Material Analysis

- Customized analytical tests and services
- Analytical method development
- Chemical reverse engineering
- Mineral and organic analysis

Cement

- Cement manufacturing
- Hydration chemistry
- Hydraulic binder formulation and usage property testing (masonry binder, road binder, grouts, ...)

Concrete

- RMX and precast concrete mix design technology
- Concrete rheology
- Admixtures
- Scale up of lab testing (batching plant/precast block machine)

Construction Engineering

- Engineering
- Jobsite operations
- Modelling
- Mechanics
- Architecture
- Construction system demonstrator

Durability

- Service life design
- Durability performance testing
- Microstructure and microscopy (optical, SEM)
- Life cycle analysis

5 Pillars of CO2 reduction

Cement Process

Source: Plan de transition sectoriel de l'industrie cimentière, ADEME

Carbon neutrality across the entire value chain

CEMBUREAU's 5C approach highlights the levers leading to **carbon neutrality** across the entire value chain of a cement/concrete group.

CLINKER
CEMENT
CONCRETE
CONSTRUCTION
CARBONATION

- **Clinker:** clinker chemistry, use of decarbonized raw materials in the raw mix...
- **Ciment:** increase in the cement/clinker ratio
- **Concrete (béton):** optimization of cement content, use of recycled and/or carbonated aggregates
- **Construction:** optimisation du placement des bétons aux besoins d'un bâtiment optimization of concrete placement to meet the needs of a building
- **Carbonatation:** natural carbonation of concrete (up to 40% of the CO2 emitted during decarbonation over the lifetime of concrete), forced carbonation (FastCarb, Solidia...)

C1, Clinker: Best Available Technology

Shutdown of 2 long dry process kilns and replacement with a precalciner kiln.

- **> 100 million Euros of investment**
- **25% reduction in carbon footprint per ton of cement: by improving energy efficiency and enabling the massive use of waste-derived fuels.**

C1, Clinker: Modification of Fuel Source (France)

PART DES COMBUSTIBLES DE SUBSTITUTION EN 2019

En pourcentage du besoin énergétique total

Source: Infociments 2020 - l'essentiel

HYPOTHESES		2015	2025	2030	2050
Taux de substitution (combustibles alternatifs / combustions fossiles)	%	38	65	80	85
Part Biomasse des combustibles alternatifs	%	49	50	60	70
Volume de combustibles Alternatifs	kT	1050	1500	1800	1800
Dont CSR	kT	272	1000	1000	1000
Part Biomasse des CSR	%	50	50	50	50

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Source: Feuille de route de décarbonation de la filière ciment, Mai 2021, Conseil National de l'Industrie

C1: Clinker: New Clinkers with modified chemistries

CSC: Low-Calcium Silicate Cement

C\$A: Calcium Sulfo Aluminate

CO₂ footprint reduction (30%) vs. OPC

- Less limestone ($CaCO_3$) in the raw mix
- Lower firing temperature ($<1450^\circ C$)

Niche market and/or developing cements

C2: Cement : lower Clinker content with Cementitious (kg_CO2/t_cement)

Already used

- Limestone
- Blast Furnace Slags
- Fly ashes

Problem of supply

New Supplementary Cementitious materials

- Calcined Clays
- Reclaimed Fly Ash
- Recycled Glasses,
- Construction Demolition Materials Fines

Calcined Clays

- Réactivité pouzzolanique proche du clinker
- No Limestone = No Process Emissions
- Low CO2 from Energy (600-700C): 0 CO2 if Biomass as fuel

Sells Launch in 2025

C3: Concrete: Carbon Footprint (kg_CO2/m3_concrete)

CO2 footprint of 1M3 RMX concrete

Poids CO2 moyen =
200 kg_CO2/m3

C3: Concrete: low CO2 recipes

- **Examples from Lafarge France:**
 - Use a low CO2 cement offer EcoPlanet
 - Low Clinker High Filler concrete
 - Use of Biochar (negative CO2 content !)

C4: Construction (kg_CO2/m2_building)

- Use the right concrete in the right place, principle of frugality : Better with Less
 - **Design tools** to help optimize construction solutions.
 - Compliance with **Regulations** (RE2020 in France):
- **CO2 limit values in terms for the construction and use Phases of a building**

360 design

Lafarge 360Design vous aide à situer votre projet par rapport aux exigences de la RE 2020*.

* Conformément au Décret n° 2021-1004 du 29 juillet 2021 relatif aux exigences de performance énergétique et environnementale des constructions de bâtiments en France métropolitaine.

MEMBRE DE **HOLCIM LAFARGE**

Optimisez l'empreinte carbone du gros œuvre de votre projet

Simulez votre projet en 5 minutes.

01. Décrivez votre projet
02. Précisez vos données
03. Optimisez votre projet
04. Allez plus loin avec nos experts

Où se situe votre projet de logement collectif ?

Ex : 92200 ou Neuilly

OPTIMISER VOTRE EMPREINTE CARBONE

C4: Construction : examples

- Optimization of concrete use in the structure
 - BIM: Building Information Modelling
 - 3D Printing
 - Mixed concrete - wood solution

C5: Natural carbonation

- At the material level
 - Carbonation of concrete = a time-dependent phenomenon known [Hamada 1969]

- Considered or not depending on the country in terms of durability
 - EU/ASIA: Corrosion of steel initiated by carbonation
 - USA: Carbonation not considered.
- Included in Environmental Product Declaration (EPDs) standards
 - EN 15804, **EN 16757**

standard NF EN 16757

Sustainability of construction works - Environmental product declarations - Product Category Rules for concrete and concrete elements

Figure BB.2 — Principe général de l'absorption de CO₂ par carbonatation du béton

C5: Natural carbonation of mortar concrete

- **At the Global Level**

- “[Global CO2 uptake by cement from 1930 to 2019](#)” by R. Guo et al.
- Analysis of Portfolio of applications
 - cement based products: concrete, mortar
 - climate: interior, sheltered, unsheltered
 - different Surface to volume ratio

- **Net Uptake:**

- **Which Product ?**

- **Where in the world ?**

Conclusions: No Silver Bullet !

CLINKER
CEMENT
CONCRETE
CONSTRUCTION
CARBONATION

5 pillars to go to net zero, including CCUS

Low CO2 cement

Calcined clays will tomorrow become the main mineral addition to cements

Context:

- 1- Gradual closure of coal-fired power plants and evolution of processes in steelworks
⇒ gradual disappearance of slag and fly ash
- 2- Only clay and limestone can respond massively and in the long term to demand
⇒ already available in cement quarry
- 3- The calcination of clay improves its reactivity and allows its use as an addition to cement
- 4- Standardization of this addition in progress

Limestone
Calcined
Clay
Cement

LC³

LOW CO₂

Availability of SCMs

CALCINED CLAYS POSITION HOLCIM AS LEADER IN GREEN CONSTRUCTION

Producing the first near-zero CO₂ calcined clay with our patented technology.

Less CO₂ than clinker

- Producing calcined clay (C) emits **4 times less CO₂** than clinker production

- With our patent-pending technology, we can go **close to zero CO₂ emissions**.

The future of green cement

- With calcined clay, we can design **cements with only 50% (or 40% CO₂ vs. OPC)**

- It is the most effective way to **design low carbon and performant cements** with **local and natural mineral compounds**.

Rolling-out globally to ensure the execution of the Net Zero Pledge and reduce our dependence to fly-ash and slag.

- The projects in the pipeline are aligned with the objectives of the **Net Zero Pledge: 3'500 kt calcined clay in 2030**

Alternative 1 - CDM fines

1. **Context:** in western/asian markets
 - a. large amount of demolition waste
 - b. limited access to resources
 - c. Returned concretes

2. Application ?

- a. **1st Switzerland** == > technical guide SIA 2049
- b. now all over Europe En 197-6

Table 1 — Cement with recycled concrete fines

Main types	Notation of the products (types of cement)		Composition (percentage by mass) ^a												
			Main constituents										Minor additional constituents		
			Clinker	Recycled concrete fines	Blast-furnace slag	Silica fume	Pozzolana		Fly ash		Burnt shale	Limestone			
							natural	natural calcined	siliceous	calcareous		L ^c		LL ^c	
Type name	Type notation	K	F	S	D ^b	P	Q	V	W	T	L ^c	LL ^c			
	Portland-recycled-fines cement	CEM II/A-F	80-94	6-20	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	0-5	
		CEM II/B-F	65-79	21-35	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	0-5	
CEM II	Portland-composite cement ^d	CEM II/A-M	80-88	6-14	←----- 6-14 ----->										0-5
		CEM II/B-M	65-79	6-29	←----- 6-29 ----->										0-5
		CEM II/C-M	50-64	6-20	←----- 16-44 ----->										0-5
CEM VI	Composite cement	CEM VI	35-49	6-20	31-59	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	0-5	

Alternative 2 - Ternary blends

1. Context:

- a. Can we do better with less == > Ternary blends ?
- b. EU project

2. Application ?

- a. now all over Europe En 107 E

Tableau 1 — Ciment Portland composé CEM II/C-M et ciment composé CEM VI

Principaux types	Notation des produits (types de ciments)		Composition (pourcentage en masse ^a)									
			Constituants principaux									
			Clinker	Laitier de haut fourneau	Fumée de silice	Pouzzolane		Cendre volante		Schiste calciné	Calcaire	
						Naturelle	Naturelle calcinée	Siliceuse	Calcique		Lc	LL ^c
Nom	Notation	K	S	D ^b	P	Q	V	W	T	Lc	LL ^c	
CEM II	Ciment Portland composé ^d	CEM II/C-M	50-64	←----- 36-50 -----→								
CEM VI	Ciment composé	CEM VI (S-P)	35-49	31-59	-	6-20	-	-	-	-	-	-
		CEM VI (S-V)	35-49	31-59	-	-	-	6-20	-	-	-	-
		CEM VI (S-L)	35-49	31-59	-	-	-	-	-	-	6-20	-
		CEM VI (S-LL)	35-49	31-59	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	6-20

Low Carbon Concrete: ECOPact

'Hope' Sculpture, COP26, Cumingar Loop Park, Glasgow

What Concrete Can We Sell?

1. Context: Concrete conforms to standards

- on-“harmonized” prescriptive standard (fixed composition)
- NF EN 1992-1-1 - Concrete in the structure

2. Why??

- structural performance of products over time
- insurability

3. Which Carbon Footprint kg_CO2/m3?

- Nature of cement kg_CO2/kg_cement
- cement dosage kg_cement/m3_concrete

4. How to deploy a non-standard concrete?

- European Technical Assessment ETA
- Performance technical file

EUROPEAN STANDARD

EN 206:2013+A2

NORME EUROPÉENNE

EUROPÄISCHE NORM

March 2021

Concrete - Specification, performance, production and conformity

Table F.1 — Recommended limiting values for composition and properties of concrete

	Exposure classes										
	No risk of corrosion or attack	Carbonation-induced corrosion				Chloride-induced corrosion					
		Sea water			Chloride other than from sea water						
	X0	XC 1	XC 2	XC 3	XC 4	XS 1	XS 2	XS 3	XD 1	XD 2	XD 3
Maximum w/c^c	-	0,65	0,60	0,55	0,50	0,50	0,45	0,45	0,55	0,55	0,45
Minimum strength class	C12/15	C20/25	C25/30	C30/37	C30/37	C30/37	C35/45	C35/45	C30/37	C30/37	C35/45
Minimum cement content ^c (kg/m ³)	-	260	280	280	300	300	320	340	300	300	320

Eurocode 2

Calcul des structures en béton

How to make concrete with less cement

1. Starting point:

- The performance of concrete is solely linked to the initial W/C ratio
- For a given cement advancement to form the W/C ratio, it fixes the Gel-Space Ratio.

c. Concept Verified for many Cements

Powers (1948)

The CO2 intensity of concrete ka CO_2/m^3 concrete/MPa

V. John CCR 2018

Introduction to Cement Hydration

What is a clinker process to make cement?

1). Decarbonation: $\text{CaCO}_3 \Rightarrow \text{CaO} + \text{CO}_2$

2). Clinkerization: it starts near 800°C but develops essentially between 1200 and 1500°C.

6). C3S increase significantly after the present of liquid phase.

5). Melting. At 1338°C, C4AF and C3A give birth to the liquid phase, which promotes the solid / solid chemical reactions between silica and lime.

4). C3A Some alumina remains, it reacts afterwards with the lime to form C3A.

3.) C4AF Iron oxide first combines with alumina and lime to form C4AF.

C= CaO, S= SiO₂, A = Al₂O₃, F=Fe₂O₃, \$ or \bar{s} = SO₃
 \bar{c} = CO₂, M = MgO

What is cement - composition ? Cement contains ground clinker, SO3 source and very often SCMs

Clinker phases: C3S (Alite), C2S (Belite), C3A (Aluminate), C4AF (Ferrite)

A typical composition of clinker

Alite/Belite/Aluminate/Ferrite= 65/20/5/10

Microscopic clinker examination (SEM)

Maximize Alite

Note: Traditionally Portland Cement consists of clinker ground with about 5% of calcium sulfate (e.g gypsum)

SO3 source: Gypsum(C\$H2), hemihydrate(C\$H0.5) and anhydrite (C\$)

SO3 is needed to prevent flash set

resulting, on a cement grain, in :

What is cement - composition ? Cement contains ground clinker, SO₃ source and very often SCMs

Supplementary cementitious materials (SCMs) : Calcined clay, Recycle concrete fines, Limestone, Pozzolan, Slag, fly ash, silica fume

Limestone

Fly ash

Slag

Silica fume

Calcined clay

Recycle concrete fines

Driving force for hydration

$$\text{Potential Energy } \Delta E = m * g * (h_f - h_i) < 0$$

$$\text{Chemical Energy } \Delta G = G_{CH} - (G_C + G_H) < 0$$

Reaction rate

Heat is released when cement reacts with water

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matdes.2023.112228>

Phase assemblage of CEM I

Avec Ca:

- Ca(OH)₂, CaCO₃, CaSO₄

Avec Ca et Si (Al)

- C-(A)-S-H

avec Al et Ca (CO₂, SO₃)

- AFm et AFt
- Hydrogrenat

Avec MgO

- Mg(OH)₂
- AFm

Reaction rate

Hydration degree

Typical hydration degree

Age (days)	OPC/ CEM I	Fly ash	Slag	Silica fume	Calcined clay (~40 %MK)
1d	45%	0%	0%	0%	0%
28d	90%	10%	45%	60%	60%
90d	95%	30%	60%	80%	70%

Strength development and Gel-space ratio

T.C. Powers

E. Freyssinet (1933)

we may surmise, as others have done before (11), that strength is some function of the concentration of the hydrated cement in the space available to it; or since hydrated cement is mostly gel, we may say it is some function of the gel-space ratio.

$$GSR = \frac{\text{Volume of hydrates}}{\text{Volume of available space}}$$

GSR is a descriptor of microstructure that captures:

- 1) the degree of hydration
- 2) the effect of water/cement ratio

$$GSR = \frac{\text{hydrates}}{\text{hydrates} + \text{Capillary porosity}}$$

- Initial stage : no hydration
 - Hydrate = 0 → GSR = 0
- Final stage : considering that all voids are replaced by hydrates
 - Capillary porosity= 0 → GSR = 1

Reaction - CaO hydration reaction with water

Constituents + water == > Hydrates

mole:	1	+	1	== >	1	
mass [g]:	56	+	18	== >	74	
volume [cm ³ /mol]:	17	+	18	== >	33	$\Delta V = -2$
G Chemical [kJ/mol]:	-603	+	-237	== >	-897	$\Delta G = -57$
H Heat [kJ/mol]:	-635	+	-286	== >	-985	$\Delta H = -64$

Lime (CaO) Hydration

- **Reaction?**
 - $\text{CaO} + \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightleftharpoons \text{Ca(OH)}_2$
- **Why does it react ?**
 - $\Delta G = -1000 \text{ kJ/kg}$
- **Water consumption?**
 - $0.32 \text{ kg_H}_2\text{O/kg_CaO}$
- **Heat released ?**
 - $\Delta H = -1150 \text{ kJ/kg}$
- **Volume change ?**

Alite (C3S) Hydration

- **Reaction ?**
 - $3\text{CaO}\cdot\text{SiO}_2 + 3.1 \text{H}_2\text{O} \Rightarrow 1.4 \text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2 + (1.6\text{CaO}\cdot\text{SiO}_2\cdot 1.7\text{H}_2\text{O})$
- **Why does it react ?**
 - $\Delta rG = -343 \text{ kJ/kg}$
- **Water consumption?**
 - $0.24 \text{ kg_H}_2\text{O}/\text{kg_C3S}$
- **Heat released ?**
 - $\Delta rH = -446 \text{ kJ/kg}$
- **Volume change ?**

■ Constituent [l/l] ■ Hydrate [l/l] ■ Water [l/l] ■ Air [l/l]

■ Constituent [l/l] ■ Hydrate [l/l] ■ Water [l/l] ■ Air [l/l]

SiO₂ - Pozzolanic reaction: CH + S ?

- **Reaction ?**
 - $1.6 \text{ Ca(OH)}_2 + \text{SiO}_2 + 0.1 \text{ H}_2\text{O} \Rightarrow (1.6\text{CaO} \cdot \text{SiO}_2 \cdot 1.7\text{H}_2\text{O})$
- **How much SiO₂ shall I add to get only C-S-H and not CH?**
 - CH/S (66/34)
- **Why does it react ?**
 - $\Delta rG = -185 \text{ kJ/kg}$
- **Water consumption?**
 - $0.011 \text{ kg_H}_2\text{O/kg_mix}$
- **Heat released ?**
 - $\Delta rH = -187 \text{ kJ/kg}$
- **Volume change ?**

Hydration + Pozzolanic reaction: $C_3S + S + H_2O$?

- **Two reactions:**
 - $3CaO \cdot SiO_2 + 3.1 H_2O \Rightarrow 1.4 Ca(OH)_2 + (1.6CaO \cdot SiO_2 \cdot 1.7H_2O)$
 - $1.6 Ca(OH)_2 + SiO_2 + 0.1 H_2O \Rightarrow (1.6CaO \cdot SiO_2 \cdot 1.7H_2O)$
 - $\frac{3}{4} 1.6CaO \cdot SiO_2 \cdot 1.7H_2O + \frac{1}{4} SiO_2 + 0.125 H_2O \Rightarrow (1.2CaO \cdot SiO_2 \cdot 1.4H_2O)$
- **How much SiO₂ shall I add to get only C-S-H (No CH)?**
 - C3S/S (72/28) if Ca/Si=1.2
 - **C3S/S (81/19) if Ca/Si=1.6**
- **Why does it react ?**
 - $\Delta rG = -382$ kJ/kg
- **Water consumption?**
 - 0.20 kg_{H2O}/kg
- **Heat released ?**
 - $\Delta rH = -467$ kJ/kg
- **Volume change ?**
 - **Comparison of C3S/S : 68/32, 81/19 and 100/0**
 - **GSR from 0.49 to 0.63 \Rightarrow CS from 30-50 MPa**
 - **Importance of DoH_{SiO2}**

Aluminate Hydration - C3A - AFm et AFt phases

- **Possible reactions:**

- $C3A + 10.5 H \Rightarrow 3/4 * 3CaO.Al_2O_3.Ca(OH)_2.12H_2O + 1/4 Al_2O_3.3H_2O$
- $C3A + Ca(OH)_2 + 12 H_2O \Rightarrow C4AH13$
- $C3A + CaCO_3 + 11 H_2O \Rightarrow 3CaO.Al_2O_3.CaCO_3.11H_2O$
- $C3A + CaSO_4.2H_2O + 10 H_2O \Rightarrow 3CaO.Al_2O_3.CaSO_4.12H_2O$
- $C3A + 3CaSO_4.2H_2O + 26 H_2O \Rightarrow 3CaO.Al_2O_3.3CaSO_4.32H_2O$

- **How much C3A / XX for complete reaction of reactants?**

- C3A/CH 78/22
- C3A/Cc 73/27
- C3A/CsH2 61/39 (Monosulfo only)
- C3A/CsH2 34/66 (Ettringite only)

- **Water consumption ?**

- from 0.4 to 0.7 kg_H2O/kg_mix !

- **Volume change ? == >**

- example for W/C=1.0, at optimum stoichiometry
- before hydration Solid/water 25/75 (in volume)

Metakaolin Reaction - CH + Cc + AS2 ?

- **Reaction:**

- $Al_2O_3 \cdot 2SiO_2 + 6.2Ca(OH)_2 + CaCO_3 + 7.2 H_2O ==> 2*(1.6CaO \cdot SiO_2 \cdot 1.7H_2O) + 3CaO \cdot Al_2O_3 \cdot CaCO_3 \cdot 11H_2O$
- $Al_2O_3 \cdot 2SiO_2 + 5Ca(OH)_2 + CaCO_3 + 8.4 H_2O ==> 2*(1.CaO \cdot SiO_2 \cdot 1.2H_2O) + 3CaO \cdot Al_2O_3 \cdot CaCO_3 \cdot 11H_2O$

- **How much CH, Cc needed?**

- High Ca/Si :
 - **CH/AS2/Cc 58/29/13**
 - **2 kg_CH/kg_AS2 and 0.45 kg_Cc/kg_AS2**
- Low Ca/Si
 - **CH/Cc/AS2 55/31/14**
 - **1.66 kg_CH/kg_AS2 and 0.45 kg_Cc/kg_AS2**

- **Water consumption ?** Mainly related to **Monocarbo**

- High Ca/Si: 0.18 kg_H2O/kg_mix
- Low Ca/Si: 0.21 kg_H2O/kg_mix

- **Volume change ? == >**

Metakaolin Reaction - C3S + Cc + AS2 ?

- **Reaction:**

- $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 2\text{SiO}_2 + 4.4 \text{ C3S} + \text{CaCO}_3 + 22 \text{ H}_2\text{O} \Rightarrow 6.4 * (1.6\text{CaO} \cdot \text{SiO}_2 \cdot 1.7\text{H}_2\text{O}) + 3\text{CaO} \cdot \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{CaCO}_3 \cdot 11\text{H}_2\text{O}$
- $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 2\text{SiO}_2 + 2.5 \text{ C3S} + \text{CaCO}_3 + 16.4 \text{ H}_2\text{O} \Rightarrow 4.5 * (1.\text{CaO} \cdot \text{SiO}_2 \cdot 1.2\text{H}_2\text{O}) + 3\text{CaO} \cdot \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{CaCO}_3 \cdot 11\text{H}_2\text{O}$

- **How much C3S, Cc needed?**

- High Ca/Si :
 - **C3S/AS2/Cc 76/17/8**
 - **4.5 kg_C3S/kg_AS2 and 0.45 kg_Cc/kg_AS2**
- Low Ca/Si
 - **C3S/Cc/AS2 55/31/14**
 - **2.6 kg_C3S/kg_AS2 and 0.45 kg_Cc/kg_AS2**

- **Water consumption ? Both Monocarbo**

- High Ca/Si: 0.29
- Low Ca/Si: 0.32

- **Volume change ? == >**

- GSR 0.65 to 0.70
- CS 50 to 60 MPa

Cement hydration - Performance summary at 90 days

STRENGTH
[MPa]

Process CO2
[t_CO2/t_cem]

H2O
[kg_H2O/kg_binder]

CO2 intensity
[kg_CO2/t_cem/Mpa]

Main steps for material characterization

- The characterization of different materials requires different steps
- Each step is crucial for reliable results

1. X-ray Diffraction
2. Thermogravimetric Analysis
3. Calorimetry
4. R3 test
5. SEM
6. ...

Steps for preparation of hydrated samples

Mixtures

Homogenization of powder samples by: hand, paddle stirrer, mixer

Storage

- In tightly closed bottles
- In a temperature - controlled room
- Before taking: stir if there is a risk of sedimentation

Stopping

- Chemical methods by solvent exchange
- Direct method

Grinding

Manual grinding with agate or porcelain mortar & sieving

63 μ m for XRD (\approx 5g)
100 μ m for TGA (\approx 1g)

- ❖ **Exposure to air can impact the mixtures** (level of **humidity**, reaction with **CO₂**)
- ❖ Hydrated phases are sensitive to grinding and heating → they can be destroyed
- ❖ Paste samples are preferred for more accurate analysis - if possible **Avoid Dilution**

Conclusions: No Silver Bullet !

CLINKER
CEMENT
CONCRETE
CONSTRUCTION
CARBONATION

5 pillars to go to net zero, including CCUS

